

COVID-19 Bibliometrics 12th – 18th October 2020

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A. Medicine and Health

October 12, 2020 (JAMA Pediatrics)

Outcomes of Neonates Born to Mothers With Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 Infection at a Large Medical Center in New York City
Dani Dumitriu, Ukachi N. Emeruwa, Erin Hanft

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2020.4298>

This cohort study describes the outcomes of neonates born to mothers with perinatal severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 infection and the infection prevention and control practices associated with these outcomes.

October 9, 2020 (IJID)

Susceptibility of obese population to COVID-19
Takefumi Kimura, Ho Namkoong

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2020.10.015>

Obesity has been reported to be a risk factor for COVID-19 severity. The authors outline several pathophysiological mechanisms that could account for the higher risk of severe disease in obese individuals.

October 6, 2020 (PNAS)

Systemic complement activation is associated with respiratory failure in COVID-19 hospitalized patients

Jan C. Holter, Soeren E. Pischke, Eline de Boer et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2010540117>

In this prospective cohort study of 39 hospitalized coronavirus disease COVID-19 patients, the authors describe systemic complement activation and its association with the development of respiratory failure. They found that several complement activation products are systemically, consistently, and long-lastingly increased from admission and during the hospital stay. Notably, the terminal sC5b-9 complement complex was associated with respiratory failure. Thus, the authors conclude that complement inhibition is an attractive therapeutic approach for the treatment of COVID-19.

October 6, 2020 (PNAS)

Decoy nanoparticles protect against COVID-19 by concurrently adsorbing viruses and inflammatory cytokines

Lang Rao, Shuai Xia, Wei Xu et. al.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2014352117>

The authors report a decoy nanoparticle against COVID-19. The decoy nanoparticles were constructed by fusing cell membrane nanovesicles derived from genetically engineered cells, which stably express SARS-CoV-2 receptor ACE2, and human monocytes, which display abundant cytokine receptors. By competing with host cells, these nanodecoys efficiently adsorb viruses and inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6 and GM-CSF. These two functionalities allow the effective intervention of viral infection and its associated immune disorder, presenting a promising therapeutic strategy for COVID-19 and other potential epidemics.

October 5, 2020 (Annals of Clin. And Translational Neurology)

Frequent neurologic manifestations and encephalopathy-associated morbidity in Covid-19 patients

Eric M. Liotta, Ayush Batra, Jeffrey R. Clark et. al.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/acn3.51210>

In this study, the authors sought to characterize the neurologic manifestations, their risk factors, and associated outcomes in hospitalized patients with COVID-19. They examined neurologic manifestations in 509 consecutive patients admitted with confirmed Covid-19 within a hospital network in Chicago, Illinois and found that neurologic manifestations occur in most hospitalized COVID-19 patients. Encephalopathy was associated with increased morbidity and mortality, independent of respiratory disease severity.

October 1, 2020 (Cell Host & Microbe)

ACTIVating Resources for the COVID-19 Pandemic: *In vivo* Models for Vaccines and Therapeutics

Judith A. Hewitt, Cathleen Lutz, William C. Florence et. al.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chom.2020.09.016>

This review provides a snapshot that recommends the suitability of animal models for testing vaccines and therapeutics. To date, mouse, hamster, ferret, guinea pig, and non-human primates have been investigated. Several species are permissive for SARS-CoV-2 replication, often exhibiting mild disease with the resolution, reflecting most human COVID-19 cases. The more severe disease develops in a few models, some associated with advanced age, a risk factor for human disease.

September 28, 2020 (Virology)

Molecular and serological characterization of SARS-CoV-2 infection among COVID-19 patients

Linghua Li, Yuanhao Liang, Fengyu Hu et al.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.virol.2020.09.008>

In this study, the authors investigated the dynamics of viral load and antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 in a longitudinal cohort of COVID-19 patients with severe and mild/moderate diseases. Their findings have shed light on viral kinetics and antibody response in COVID-19 patients and provide scientific evidence for infection control and patient management.

[September 24, 2020 \(Virology\)](#)

Favipiravir versus other antiviral or standard of care for COVID-19 treatment: a rapid systematic review and meta-analysis

Shrestha, D.B., Budhathoki, P., Khadka, S. *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12985-020-01412-z>

The authors conduct a systematic review and meta-analysis on efficacy and safety of the drug Favipiravir as a treatment for COVID-19. They analysed 9 qualitative and 4 quantitative studies. They found that there is a significant clinical and radiological improvement following treatment with favipiravir in comparison to the standard of care with no significant differences on viral clearance, oxygen support requirement and side effect profiles.

[September 14, 2020 \(The Lancet\)](#)

Lancet COVID-19 Commission Statement on the occasion of the 75th session of the UN General Assembly

The Lancet COVID-19 Commissioners, Task Force Chairs, and Commission Secretariat

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)31927-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)31927-9)

The *Lancet* COVID-19 Commission, launched on July 9, 2020 aims to offer practical solutions to the four main global challenges posed by the pandemic: suppressing the pandemic by means of pharmaceutical and non-pharmaceutical interventions, overcoming humanitarian emergencies, restructuring public and private finances in the wake of the pandemic, and rebuilding the world economy in an inclusive, resilient, and sustainable way. This initial Statement of the Commission marks the occasion of the opening of the 75th Session of the UN General Assembly on Sept 15, 2020.

[September 11, 2020 \(Annals of Int. Medicine\)](#)

Every Body Counts: Measuring Mortality From the COVID-19 pandemic

Mathew V. Kiang, Rafael A. Irazarry, Caroline O. Buckee *et. al.*

<https://doi.org/10.7326/M20-3100>

This article discusses the current difficulties of disaster death attribution and describes the strengths and limitations of relying on death counts from death certificates, estimations of indirect deaths and estimations of excess mortality.

August 27, 2020 (Virologica journal)

Characterization of accessory genes in coronavirus genomes

Michel, C.J., Mayer, C., Poch, O. *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12985-020-01402-1>

Coronavirus genomes code for a ORF1a/ ORF1ab polyprotein and four structural proteins widely studied as major drug targets. The genomes also contain a variable number of open reading frames (ORFs) coding for accessory proteins that are not essential for virus replication but appear to have a role in pathogenesis. The authors applied a computational tool GOFIX to characterize potential ORFs in SARS-CoV-2 and related genomes including SARS-CoV and SARS-like viruses from bat, civet and pangolin hosts, focusing on the accessory proteins.

August 19, 2020 (The Lancet Regional Health – Western Pacific)

Large-scale epidemiological monitoring of the COVID-19 epidemic in Tokyo

Daisuke Yoneoka, Yuta Tanoue, Takayuki Kawashima *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanwpc.2020.100016>

A chatbot-based healthcare system named COOPERA (COvid-19: Operation for Personalized Empowerment to Render smart prevention And AN care seeking) was developed to survey the Japanese epidemiological situation in real-time. COOPERA asked questions regarding personal information, location, preventive actions, COVID-19 related symptoms and their residence. The authors found that this new system can monitor the epidemiological situation and can provide insights to assist political decision to tackle the epidemic.

B. Science and Engineering

October 10, 2020 (Computers in Biology and Medicine)

Multi-omics-based identification of SARS-CoV-2 infection biology and candidate drugs against COVID-19

Debmalya Barh, Sandeep Tiwari, Marianna E. Weener *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2020.104051>

The authors use multi-omics (interactome, proteome, transcriptome, and bibliome) data to analyse the biological events associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection and identify several candidate drugs against this viral disease. Nearly 70% of the identified agents that are previously suggested to have anti-COVID-19 effects or under clinical trials. Among our identified drugs, the ones that are not yet tested, need validation with caution while an appropriate drug combination from these candidate drugs along with a SARS-CoV-2 specific antiviral agent is needed for effective COVID-19 management.

October 7, 2020 (Virology Journal)

The effect of temperature on persistence of SARS-CoV-2 on common surfaces

Shane Riddell, Sarah Goldie, Andrew Hill et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12985-020-01418-7>

This study measured the survival rates of infectious SARS-CoV-2, suspended in a standard ASTM E2197 matrix, on several common surface types. All experiments were carried out in the dark, to negate any effects of UV light. Inoculated surfaces were incubated at 20 °C, 30 °C and 40 °C and sampled at various time points. Their findings demonstrate SARS-CoV-2 can remain infectious for significantly longer periods than generally considered possible. These results could be used to inform improved risk mitigation procedures to prevent the fomite spread of COVID-19.

September 29, 2020 (Bioorganic Chemistry)

A perspective on potential target proteins of COVID-19: Comparison with SARS-CoV for designing new small molecules

Devendra Kumar, Gaurav Chauhan, Sourav Kalra et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioorg.2020.104326>

These chemists explored three major targets namely; SARS-CoV-2 spike (S) protein, RNA dependent RNA polymerase, and 3CL or Mpro Protease for the inhibition of SARS-CoV-2. These targets have attracted the attention of the medicinal chemists working on computer-aided drug design in developing new small molecules that might inhibit these targets for combating COVID-19 disease. We have observed that both the coronaviruses share around 80% similarity in their amino acid sequence.

This study will help the medicinal chemists to understand the key amino acids essential for interactions at the active site of target proteins in SARS-CoV-2, based on their similarity with earlier reported viruses. In this review, we have also described the lead molecules under various clinical trials for their efficacy against COVID-19.

September 25, 2020 (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences)

Speech can produce jet-like transport relevant to asymptomatic spreading of virus

Manouk Abkarian, Simon Mendez, Nan Xue et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2012156117>

Droplet emission occurs during the speech, but the lack of understanding prevents informed public health guidance for risk reduction and mitigation strategies. The authors analyze flows during breathing and speaking, including phonetic features, using numerical simulations and laboratory experiments. The authors document the spatiotemporal structure of the expelled airflow. Phonetic characteristics of sound like “P” lead to enhanced directed transport of jet-like flows. They highlight three distinct temporal scaling laws for the transport distance of exhaled material including 1)

transport over a short distance (<0.5 m) in a fraction of a second, with large angular variations due to the complexity of speech; 2) a longer distance, ~1 m, and 3) a distance out to about 2 m. This work will highlight the role of ventilation, aerosol transport in disease transmission for humans and other animals and provide a better understanding of linguistic aerodynamics, i.e., aerophonetics.

[August 24, 2020 \(Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences\)](#)

A network-based explanation of why most COVID-19 infection curves are linear

Stefan Thurner, Peter Klimek, Rudolf Hanel

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2010398117>

The authors explain this puzzling observation based on the structure of contact networks. We show that for any given transmission rate there exists a critical number of social contacts below which linear growth and low infection prevalence must occur. Above this number traditional epidemiological dynamics take place, e.g., as in susceptible–infected–recovered (SIR) models. They reproduce actual infection curves with high precision. They compare the United States and Austria (as examples for one country that initially did not impose measures and one that responded with a severe lockdown early on).

C. Social Sciences, Humanities and Public Policies

[October 6, 2020 \(Journal of Public Affairs\)](#)

The geography of the effectiveness and consequences of Covid-19 measures: Global evidence

Simplice A. Asongu, Samba Diop & Joseph Nnanna.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/pa.2483>

This useful paper takes a global look at the varying effectiveness of lockdown, movement restrictions, governance and economic, social distancing, and public health measures in tackling COVID-19. The empirical evidence is based on the comparative difference in means tests and correlation analyses. The comparative findings reveal that:

- (a) from a holistic perspective, only European countries have favourably benefited from the Covid-19 measures;
- (b) lockdown measures at the global level have not been significant in reducing the pandemic;
- (c) the restriction of movement measure has been relevant in curbing the spread in the American continent;
- (d) the enforcement of the social distancing measures has been productive in Europe and counter-productive in Africa;
- (e) governance and economic measures have exclusively been relevant in Europe; and (f) overall public health measures have not had the desired outcomes in flattening the infection curve. The authors believe this to be

because most of the underlying measures are oriented toward people already infected or are “awareness decisions”.

[September 25, 2020 \(Journal of Business Research\)](#)

Convergence innovation in the digital age and in the COVID-19 pandemic crisis

Sang M. Lee, Silvana Trimi

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.09.041>

This paper presents the concept of convergence innovation (CI), which is “powered by the exponential fusion effect of the various objects, technologies, ideas, and strategies, as a new sustainable core competence of organizations”. The paper also rather optimistically explores how CI can be a catalyst for managing the current COVID-19 pandemic and charting the path to post-crisis.

[September 24, 2020 \(Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences\)](#)

The rise of COVID-19 cases is associated with support for world leaders

Kai Chi Yam, Joshua Conrad Jackson, Christopher M. Barnes et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2009252117>

This paper finds a strong and significant positive association between new daily confirmed and total confirmed COVID-19 cases and support for the heads of government across 11 countries/regions and 50 USA States. The authors cautiously suggest that their findings could have important voting implications. If citizens do “rally ‘round the flag,” then-upcoming elections during or in the aftermath of COVID-19 could potentially be advantageous for some incumbents.

[September 13, 2020 \(Social Science & Medicine\)](#)

Health risks and outcomes that disproportionately affect women during the Covid-19 pandemic: A review

Jade Connor, Sarina Madhavan, Mugdha Mokashi et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113364>

This short but extensively referenced paper assesses data from previous disease outbreaks coupled with literature from the Covid-19 pandemic to examine the impact of gender on women's SARS-CoV-2 exposure and disease risks and overall health status during the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors admit that due to the evolving nature of the pandemic, data regarding gendered COVID-19 health differences are limited. Much of the literature cited here regarding gender and disease outbreaks come from the SARS, Ebola, and Zika outbreaks. Nevertheless, the authors conclude that the pandemic will have immediate and long-term effects on women's health, and they highlight the importance of gender analysis in its planning and response. They propose that when preparing for the aftermath of Covid-19, healthcare providers and administrators should take a gender-inclusive approach.